

Supplementary Information for
Quantum Geometry of an Electron:
the Golden Number and Internal Half-Oscillator

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*This article was written at the period of my unpaid leave from the Institute of Physics, Polish Academy of Sciences, Aleja Lotników 32/46, PL 02 668 Warsaw, Poland. During this time I was employed at the Department of Condensed Matter Physics, Masaryk University, Kotlářská 2, CZ-61137 Brno, Czech Republic, but the reported curiosity-driven analysis was performed beyond the scope of my duties as a member of the teams I worked with, therefore it seems to be appropriate to publish it on my own responsibility.

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1. Derivation of the equality $\langle O_e \rangle = 1/2 \lambda_0$ from the general formulas

$$\langle O_e \rangle = 2\pi \langle R_e \rangle = 2\pi \frac{\hbar}{2m_e c} = 2\pi \frac{hc}{2\pi 2m_e c^2} = \frac{hc}{2E} = 1/2 \lambda_0 \quad (43)$$

2. Equations describing a linear plane electromagnetic wave

$$E(x, t) = E_0 \sin\left(2\pi vt - \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} x\right) \quad (44)$$

$$B(x, t) = B_0 \sin\left(2\pi vt - \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} x\right) \quad (45)$$

Let's introduce the following parameters:

$$k = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \quad (46)$$

$$x = c(t - t_0) \quad (47)$$

$$\theta = \frac{4\pi c}{\lambda}(t - t_0) = 2kx \text{ [rad]} \quad (48)$$

$$\langle R_e \rangle = \frac{\lambda}{4\pi} = (2k)^{-1} \quad (49)$$

- a) Equations of linear plane electromagnetic wave, expressed analogously to equations (7)-(9), as a function of the position of the wave-front (x) and its length (λ)

$$\vec{c}: \begin{cases} x_c = x \\ y_c = 0 \\ z_c = 0 \end{cases} \quad (50)$$

$$\vec{E}: \begin{cases} x_E = x \\ y_E = E'_0 \sin\left(\frac{4\pi}{\lambda} x\right) \\ z_E = 0 \end{cases} \quad (51)$$

$$\vec{B}: \begin{cases} x_B = x \\ y_B = 0 \\ z_B = B'_0 \sin\left(\frac{4\pi}{\lambda} x\right) \end{cases} \quad (52)$$

- b) Equations of linear plane electromagnetic wave as a function of time (t) and wave number (k)

$$\vec{c}: \begin{cases} x_c = c(t - t_0) \\ y_c = 0 \\ z_c = 0 \end{cases} \quad (53)$$

$$\vec{E}: \begin{cases} x_E = c(t - t_0) \\ y_E = E'_0 \sin(2kc(t - t_0)) \\ z_E = 0 \end{cases} \quad (54)$$

$$\vec{B}: \begin{cases} x_B = c(t - t_0) \\ y_B = 0 \\ z_B = B'_0 \sin(2kc(t - t_0)) \end{cases} \quad (55)$$

As can be seen, in equations (50)-(55) the wavelength number of the photon has been doubled in relation to that of equations (44)-(45). This was necessary to obtain correct wave packet diagrams while simultaneously meeting the condition of maintaining a uniform equation convention with respect to the analogous form of electron description.

3. Equations describing an electron at rest as electromagnetic wave propagating along a circle

- a) Equations (7)-(9) as a function of the position of the wave front (x) and its wavelength (λ)

$$\vec{c}: \begin{cases} x_c = \frac{\lambda}{4\pi} \cos\left(\frac{4\pi}{\lambda} x\right) \\ y_c = \frac{\lambda}{4\pi} \sin\left(\frac{4\pi}{\lambda} x\right) \\ z_c = 0 \end{cases} \quad (56)$$

$$\vec{E}: \begin{cases} x_E = \left(\frac{\lambda}{4\pi} - E'_0 \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} x\right)\right) \cos\left(\frac{4\pi}{\lambda} x\right) \\ y_E = \left(\frac{\lambda}{4\pi} - E'_0 \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} x\right)\right) \sin\left(\frac{4\pi}{\lambda} x\right) \\ z_E = 0 \end{cases} \quad (57)$$

$$\vec{B}: \begin{cases} x_B = \frac{\lambda}{4\pi} \cos\left(\frac{4\pi}{\lambda} x\right) \\ y_B = \frac{\lambda}{4\pi} \sin\left(\frac{4\pi}{\lambda} x\right) \\ z_B = B'_0 \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} x\right) \end{cases} \quad (58)$$

- b) Equations (7)-(9) as a function of time (t) and wave number (k)

$$\vec{c}: \begin{cases} x_c = (2k)^{-1} \cos(2kc(t - t_0)) \\ y_c = (2k)^{-1} \sin(2kc(t - t_0)) \\ z_c = 0 \end{cases} \quad (59)$$

$$\vec{E}: \begin{cases} x_E = ((2k)^{-1} - E'_0 \sin kx) \cos(2kc(t - t_0)) \\ y_E = ((2k)^{-1} - E'_0 \sin kx) \sin(2kc(t - t_0)) \\ z_E = 0 \end{cases} \quad (60)$$

$$\vec{B}: \begin{cases} x_B = (2k)^{-1} \cos(2kc(t - t_0)) \\ y_B = (2k)^{-1} \sin(2kc(t - t_0)) \\ z_B = B'_0 \sin(kc(t - t_0)) \end{cases} \quad (61)$$

4. Calculation of the average magnetic moment ($\langle \mu_i \rangle$) coming from a single phase of an electron oscillation

$$\langle \mu_i \rangle = IS = \frac{q}{t} \pi \langle R_e \rangle^2 = \frac{e}{\frac{2\pi \langle R_e \rangle}{c}} \pi \langle R_e \rangle^2 = \frac{ec}{2\pi \langle R_e \rangle} \pi \langle R_e \rangle^2 = \frac{ec \langle R_e \rangle}{2} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{e\hbar}{2m_e} = \frac{1}{2} \mu_B \quad (62)$$

where: I – current intensity, S – surface area, e – elementary charge (equal to the charge of a single electron), μ_B – Bohr magneton.

5. Mathematical properties of the golden number

$$\varphi = \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2} \text{ (definition)} \quad (63)$$

$$\varphi + 1 = \varphi^2 \quad (64)$$

$$\frac{1}{\varphi} = \varphi - 1 \quad (65)$$

$$\frac{1}{\varphi} - 1 = \frac{1}{\varphi} - \frac{\varphi}{\varphi} = \frac{1-\varphi}{\varphi} = -\frac{\varphi-1}{\varphi} = -\frac{1}{\frac{\varphi}{\varphi-1}} = -\frac{1}{\varphi^2} \quad (66)$$

$$\varphi + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} = 2 \quad (67)$$

6. The proof of equivalence of the uncertainty principle for photons given in (25) with its original version

The original version of the uncertainty principle for photons from [30] (given in (25) in a form revealing the golden number presence) is following:

$$\Delta R \Delta P \geq \hbar \frac{3}{2} \sqrt{1 + \frac{4\sqrt{5}}{9}} \quad (68)$$

Let's transform the right side of the above inequality applying mathematical properties of the golden number:

$$\begin{aligned} \hbar \frac{3}{2} \sqrt{1 + \frac{4\sqrt{5}}{9}} &= \hbar \frac{3}{2} \sqrt{1 + \frac{4(2\varphi-1)}{9}} = \hbar \frac{3}{2} \sqrt{1 + \frac{8\varphi-4}{9}} = \hbar \frac{3}{2} \sqrt{\frac{9+8\varphi-4}{9}} = \hbar \frac{3}{2} \sqrt{\frac{8\varphi+5}{9}} = \hbar \frac{3}{2} \sqrt{\frac{4\varphi+4+4\varphi+1}{9}} = \\ \hbar \frac{3}{2} \sqrt{\frac{4(\varphi+1)+4\varphi+1}{9}} &= \hbar \frac{3}{2} \sqrt{\frac{4\varphi^2+4\varphi+1}{9}} = \hbar \frac{3}{2} \sqrt{\frac{(2\varphi+1)^2}{9}} = \hbar \frac{3}{2} \sqrt{\left(\frac{2\varphi+1}{3}\right)^2} = \hbar \frac{3}{2} \frac{2\varphi+1}{3} = \hbar \frac{2\varphi+1}{2} = \hbar \left(\varphi + \frac{1}{2}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (69)$$

7. Quantum parameters characterizing both phases of electromagnetic oscillations of an electron

Parameter	Parameter symbol	Phase	
		„Positive” (+)	„Negative” (-)
Quantum electron circumference	O^i	$2\pi \langle R_e \rangle \frac{1}{\varphi^2} = \frac{\lambda_c}{2} \frac{1}{\varphi^2}$	$2\pi \langle R_e \rangle \varphi = \frac{\lambda_c}{2} \varphi$
Phase duration	t^i	$\frac{2\pi \langle R_e \rangle}{c} \frac{1}{\varphi^2} = \frac{\lambda_c}{2c} \frac{1}{\varphi^2}$	$\frac{2\pi \langle R_e \rangle}{c} \varphi = \frac{\lambda_c}{2c} \varphi$
Angular velocity of wave-front propagation	ω^i	$\frac{c}{\langle R_e \rangle} \varphi^2$	$\frac{c}{\langle R_e \rangle} \frac{1}{\varphi}$
Magnetic moment	μ^i	$ec \frac{\langle R_e \rangle}{2} \frac{1}{\varphi^2}$	$ec \frac{\langle R_e \rangle}{2} \varphi$
Energy corresponding with the wavelength	E^i	$\frac{hc}{4\pi \langle R_e \rangle} \varphi^2 = m_e c^2 \varphi^2$ $= m_e c^2 (\varphi + 1)$	$\frac{hc}{4\pi \langle R_e \rangle} \frac{1}{\varphi} = m_e c^2 \frac{1}{\varphi}$ $= m_e c^2 (\varphi - 1)$
Internal binding potential energy	E_p^i	$-m_e c^2 \left(\varphi - \frac{1}{2}\right)$	$-m_e c^2 \left(\varphi - \frac{3}{2}\right)$
Energy stored as mass	E_m^i	$\frac{3}{2} m_e c^2$	$\frac{1}{2} m_e c^2$

8. Half-oscillator equations for the virial approximation

$$E_p^i = -\hbar\langle\omega\rangle \frac{\left(\frac{1}{\varphi^3}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}-n'\varphi}}{1+\left(\frac{1}{\varphi^3}\right)^{-\varphi}} = -\hbar\langle\omega\rangle \frac{(2\alpha_s)^{\frac{1}{3}-n'\varphi}}{1+(2\alpha_s)^{-\varphi}} \quad (70)$$

$$R^i = \frac{1}{2n'+\frac{1}{2}+\alpha_s} \langle R_e \rangle \quad (71)$$

$$E_\lambda^i = \frac{1}{2} \hbar\langle\omega\rangle \left(2n' + \frac{1}{2} + \alpha_s\right) \quad (72)$$

$$E_m^i = \frac{1}{2} \hbar\langle\omega\rangle \left(2n' + \frac{1}{2} + \alpha_s - 2 \frac{(2\alpha_s)^{\frac{1}{3}-n'\varphi}}{1+(2\alpha_s)^{-\varphi}}\right) \quad (73)$$

9. Quantum electrodynamic calculations of the anomalous magnetic moment of an electron

Quantum electrodynamic calculations of the anomalous magnetic moment of an electron are described in details in the Theoretical Physics Reference 0.5 documentation, 8.3. Quantum Electrodynamics (QED), available online: <https://www.theoretical-physics.com/dev/quantum/qed.html> (accessed: 19.05.2025). Accordingly to this source, the procedure is based on the Green's functions and applies the fine-structure constant (α); at the first stage the following rough estimation of $(a_e)_{QED}$ is obtained:

$$(a_e)_{QED} = \frac{\alpha}{2\pi} \approx 0.0011614 \quad (74)$$

Then, the $(a_e)_{QED}$ value is refined that leads to the final formula given below:

$$(a_e)_{QED} = A_1 \left(\frac{\alpha}{\pi}\right) + A_2 \left(\frac{\alpha}{\pi}\right)^2 + A_3 \left(\frac{\alpha}{\pi}\right)^3 + A_4 \left(\frac{\alpha}{\pi}\right)^4 + A_5 \left(\frac{\alpha}{\pi}\right)^5 \quad (75)$$

where: $A_1 = 1/2$, $A_2 = -0.328478965579194$, $A_3 = 1.18124145658720$, $A_4 = -1.91298(84)$, $A_5 = 7.795(336)$.

It should be added that only the A_1 - A_3 parameters in the equation (75) are possible to be determined analytically; A_4 and A_5 are found numerical. The final result is following:

$$(a_e)_{QED} = 0.00115965218164 \quad (76)$$

10. Half-oscillator calculation of the anomalous magnetic moment of an electron

Due to the fact that magnetic moment is proportional to the particle's quantum radius (see equation (62)), the anomalous magnetic moment of an electron is given by:

$$a_e = \frac{1}{2} \frac{(R^+ + R^-)}{\langle R_e \rangle} - 1 \quad (77)$$

It is possible to calculate R^i directly from (36) or (71), which is the same.